

■ *pla*
 ■ *pst* (pPCP1)
 ■ *yopD* (pCD1)
 ■ *YPMT1.67c* (pMT1)
 ■ *YPO3619* (Chromosome)

95% family-wise confidence level

■ *pla*
■ pPCP1
■ pCD1
■ pMT1
■ Chromosome